

EXPERIMENTAL STUDY OF LIGHTNING DIRECT EFFECTS ON CFRP UNDER ATMOSPHERIC PRESSURE AIR AND REDUCED PRESSURE AIR

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Keywords: CFRP, Lightning strike, Direct effect, Delamination

ABSTRACT

This study examined lightning strike damage behaviours of carbon fibre reinforced plastic (CFRP) laminates under atmospheric pressure air (0.1 MPa) and reduced pressure air (0.02 MPa) to evaluate the effect of atmospheric environment on lightning damage behaviour. Simulated lightning current in accordance with SAE-ARP 5412B was applied to each specimen. The maximum current peak value was approximately 40 kA. CFRP laminates under reduced pressure air exhibited slight damage compared with that under atmospheric pressure air. High-speed observation revealed that the arc was directly discharged to copper frame around a specimen from discharge probe at 24 μ s after application of impulse current under reduced pressure air. These experimental results suggest that arc root behaviour strongly affect the lightning strike damage.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fibre reinforced plastic (CFRP) have been widely applied to primary aircraft structures because of their excellent mechanical properties. One of the serious hazards for aircraft is lightning strike during operation. It is widely understood that CFRP is seriously damaged by lightning compared to aluminium alloys. Therefore, CFRP structures need special design methodology against lightning strike. To reduce the threat of lightning strike damage, metal mesh such as expanded copper foil (ECF) is applied to the surface of CFRP structures as a lightning strike protection (LSP) system [1, 2]. It is effective against lightning strike, however, complete protection is still difficult. When aircrafts were struck by lightning, inspection and repair are required before the next flight, resulting in increasing the operation cost. Understanding lightning strike damage mechanisms in detail is important for developing aircraft structures using CFRP and further improvement of safety.

Damage behaviour of CFRP laminates subjected to lightning have been studied experimentally in some earlier works [3-9]. These works reported that various damage modes such as delamination, carbon fibre breakage, thermal decomposition of matrix resin, matrix crack and others were observed. Lightning strike event occurs in extremely short period. Moreover, lightning strike damage are caused by electrical, thermal and mechanical phenomena such as Joule heating, thermal decomposition of matrix resin, combustion, shock wave, Lorentz force and others [10]. Because of complexities of these phenomena, the effect of each phenomenon on lightning strike damage and how they interact with each other are not clarified in detail. Especially, the effect of atmospheric gas species and pressure on the damage of CFRP exposed to impulse current have not been evaluated in the relevant literature. Testing environment affects combustion of carbon fibre, matrix resin and pyrolysis gas, progression of arc attachment area, behaviour of surface discharge and acoustic force, and others. Understanding the effect of these phenomena on lightning strike damage is important to consider damage mechanisms as well as testing method.

The objective of this study is to investigate the effect of atmospheric environment on lightning damage behaviour. To achieve this objective, simulated lightning current tests were carried out under atmospheric pressure air (0.1 MPa) and reduced pressure air (0.02 MPa). Aerospace grade CFRP with toughened epoxy matrix resin were evaluated. Lightning strike damage behaviour during the simulated lightning testing was observed using a video camera and a high-speed camera. After the testing, lightning strike damage on the surface was visually observed, and the internal damage was detected using ultra-sonic inspection. The damage mechanisms caused by lightning strike in atmospheric pressure air and reduced pressure air were discussed.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Material and specimen

Cross-ply laminates of CF/epoxy (IMS60/#133) were prepared for the simulated lightning strike tests. Unidirectional prepreg tapes obtained from Teijin Co. Ltd., Japan were laminated as $[0/90]_{4s}$, and were moulded using an autoclave for 2 hours at 180 °C. Each specimen had 150 mm width and 150 mm length, and 2.2 mm thickness.

2.2 Simulated lightning current tests under different atmosphere

Impulse current tests were conducted under air (0.1 MPa) and reduced pressure air (0.02 MPa) to clarify the effect of atmospheric environment on the lightning strike damage. An impulse current generator (Otowa Electric Co., Ltd., Japan) in National Composite Centre, Nagoya University, Japan was used for the simulated lightning current testing (Fig. 1 (a)). The tests were carried out in an acrylic chamber, which had 380 mm diameter and 390 mm height, as shown Fig. 1 (b). For the atmospheric pressure (0.1 MPa) testing, the lid at the top of the chamber was fixed with bolts after setting a specimen to jig. For reduced pressure testing, the test chamber was evacuated using a rotary vane vacuum pump, and the internal pressure was controlled as 20% atmospheric pressure (0.02 MPa).

The outer edge of a specimen was fixed in a copper jig which was electrically connected to the ground. A positive impulse current was applied to the central part of the specimen from a needle type discharged probe. The distance between the discharged probe tip and the specimen was set as 2 mm.

Lightning strike behaviour was observed using a video camera at 30 fps, and a high-speed camera (HPV-1, Shimadzu Corporation) at 250 kfps. Non-destructive inspection (NDI) was conducted from the back surface using ultrasonic equipment (HIS-3; Krautkramer Japan Co. Ltd., Japan) to evaluate internal damage (delamination). The scanning pitch was 0.50 mm × 0.50 mm. The scanning probe had 3.5 MHz of frequency.

Figure 1: Experimental set up for simulated lightning current tests.

2.3 Simulated lightning current waveform

The component A waveform is expressed with the current peak value (I_{peak}), the front time from nominal origin to I_{peak} (T_1) and the duration from the nominal origin to 50% I_{peak} through I_{peak} (T_2) as parameters. In addition, action integral, which denotes a proportional value to the electrical energy, are defined as shown below.

$$Action\ integral = \int I^2 dt \quad (1)$$

Therein, I and t signify the electrical current and time, respectively.

The current peak value is defined as 200 kA in SAE-ARP 5412B [11], however, that was modified to 40 kA in this study because specimen size was too small. The wave form is presented in Fig. 2. T_1/T_2 was approximately 28/87 μ s. Lightning waveform condition for each specimen were summarized in Table 1.

Figure 2: Typical lightning waveform of 40 kA.

Material	Atmosphere and pressure	Peak current I_{peak} (kA)	Waveform T_1/T_2 (μ s)	Action integral (kA^2s)
CF/epoxy	Air (0.1 MPa)	41.2	27.5/87.4	91.8
	Air (0.02 MPa)	43.0	29.7/88.0	100

Table 1: Testing conditions for applied impulse current.

3 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Observation of lightning strike damage using a video camera and a high-speed camera

Fig. 3 shows typical images at 0.1, 0.5 and 1.0 s after application of impulse current, which were captured using a video camera. In atmospheric pressure air (0.1 MPa), flame was observed at the same time application of impulse current. The flame disappeared at 3 s after application of impulse current, and white smoke was observed for several seconds. On the other hand, no flame was observed under reduced pressure air (0.02 MPa).

Fig. 4 shows high-speed images at 20, 52 and 100 μ s after application of impulse current, which were captured using a high-speed camera. The duration time of impulse current flowing was approximately 136 μ s. Pyrolysis gas was observed just after the impulse current application. Pyrolysis gas was generated along the transverse direction (90°) of the top layer from the arc attachment point under atmospheric pressure air (0.1 MPa) and reduced pressure air (0.02 MPa). It was connected to the copper flamm at 24 μ s under reduced pressure air (0.02 MPa). This phenomenon was not observed under atmospheric pressure air (0.1 MPa).

Figure 3: Damage behaviour 0.1, 0.5 and 1.0 s after application of impulse current.

Figure 4: Arc root behaviour under atmospheric pressure air (0.1 MPa) and reduced pressure air (0.02 MPa).

3.2 Evaluation of the specimens after lightning strike

Fig. 5 (a) shows arc attachment surface of test specimens after impulse current tests. Carbon fibre was broken around an arc attachment area under air and reduced pressure air. Internal layer was exposed caused by the lift-up of top surface along the longitudinal direction (0°). The length of carbon fibre breakage in transverse direction of the top layer was approximately 135 mm under air (0.1 MPa). On the other hand, under reduced pressure air (0.02 MPa), carbon fibre breakage in the transverse direction was not observed on the surface. No damage such as carbon fibre breakage or thermal decomposition of matrix resin was observed on the back surface of the specimens under both test conditions.

The ultrasonic inspection results are presented in Fig. 5 (b). Right and left side were reversed in Fig. 5 (b) to compare directly with Fig. 5 (a). Delamination was detected within approximately 0.7 mm (5 layers) from the front surface under atmospheric pressure air (0.1 MPa). Under reduced pressure air (0.02 MPa), no significant delamination was observed.

Figure 5: Lightning strike damage under atmospheric pressure air (0.1 MPa) and reduced pressure air (0.02 MPa).

3.3 Discussions

Experimental results revealed that lightning strike damage under reduced pressure air (0.02 MPa) was significantly suppressed compared with that under atmospheric pressure air (0.1 MPa). The observation results of high-speed camera and the damage after application of impulse current suggest that the arc root area progressed along the transverse direction (90°) of the top layer. Fig. 6 shows the arc root length along the transverse direction (90°) of the top layer in each atmospheric environment, which were measured from high-speed observation. The high-speed observation results indicate that the impulse current was directly discharged from the probe to the copper frame at the edge of a specimen after $24 \mu\text{s}$. It implies that the net electric current inside CFRP is little. This phenomenon that electric current progresses on the surface of the material is called as surface discharge [12]. In addition, under reduced pressure air, the influence of mechanical load by the plasma gas (shock wave) is supposed to be much smaller than those under the atmospheric pressure air. This might be one of the reasons of reduction of damage compared with that under atmospheric air.

Further studies are required to understand the mechanisms of the arc root change under different test environments. However, these experimental results suggest arc root behaviour on the arc attachment surface strongly affect lightning strike damage.

Figure 6: Time history of arc root length in transverse direction and impulse current.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This study examined the effect of atmospheric environment on the lightning strike damage behaviour. Lightning strike damage behaviour of CF/epoxy under atmospheric pressure air (0.1 MPa) and reduced pressure air (0.02 MPa) was investigated. The lightning strike damage such as carbon fibre breakage, changes in colour and delamination under reduced pressure air (0.02 MPa) was slight compared to that under atmospheric pressure air (0.1 MPa). The observation results obtained by high-speed camera revealed that arc was directly discharged to copper frame from discharge probe at 24 μs after application of impulse current under reduced pressure air (0.02 MPa). These experimental results suggest that arc root behaviour on the arc attachment surface strongly affect lightning strike damage.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work supported by JSPS KAKENHI Grant Number 19H02342, 19J22413, and 17K14881. We would like to give special thanks to Dr. Hiromitsu Miyaki of JAXA, Mr. Katsunori Takita of IHI Jet Service Co., Ltd., Mr. Tatsuya Shimoe of Tokyo Composite Design & Manufacturing (TCM, Japan) and Mr. Ryuunosuke Minegishi of the graduate student of Tokyo University of Agriculture and Technology, for their technical support.

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